

Isoindolinones (Phthalimidines)[†]

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Manuscript received 30 April 2001

Contents

1. Introduction
2. Structure of isoindole
3. Naturally occurring isoindole and isoindolinone (phthalimidine) derivatives
4. Biologically important isoindole and isoindolinone (phthalimidine) derivatives
5. Isoindolinone in the synthesis of drugs
6. Isoindolinone in the synthesis of natural products
7. Classical methods
- 7A.1. Synthesis of isoindolinones (phthalimidines) through Gabriel's procedure
- 7A.2. Alkylidene isoindolinones through Grignard procedure
- 7A.3. Synthesis of isoindolinones through lithiation procedure
- 7A.4. 3-Alkylidene isoindolinones through Wittig reaction
- 7A.5. Synthesis of isoindolinones through Diels-Alder reaction
- 7A.6. Synthesis of isoindolinones through reduction processes
- 7A.7. Synthesis of isoindolinones through condensation reactions
- 7A.8. Synthesis of isoindolinones through rearrangement reactions
- 7A.9. Synthesis of isoindolinones through photochemical reactions
- 7A.10. Synthesis of isoindolinones through miscellaneous processes
- 7B. Synthesis of isoindolinones through metal mediated reactions
8. Synthesis of isoindolinones through palladium-copper catalyzed reactions

1. Introduction

Isoindole **1** is isomeric with indole **2** which comprises a benzene ring fused with a pyrrole nucleus^{1a}. The parent compound and the 2-unsubstituted derivatives can tautomerize with the 1H isomer, i.e. isoindolenine or (1H-isoindole) **3**^{1a,b}. Isoindole is much more unstable compared with indole and undergoes rapid oxidation in air to form polymers^{1a}. Isoindole is thermodynamically more stable than its isoindolenine isomer at room temperature^{1a}. The next stable reduction state of isoindole is isoindoline **4**. Isoindolinone (phthalimidine) **5** is the more stable derivative of isoindole.

To generate isoindole, phthalimidine ring requires nucleophilic addition or reduction at the carbonyl group followed by elimination of water^{1c}. The chemical instability of isoindole **1** is well documented^{1b} which prevented its isolation and detailed characterization until 1972 and 1973³. The preparation of the first isoindole derivative, i.e. *N*-methylisoindole **6** in 1951² and the unsubstituted parent isoindole **1** in 1972 and 1973³ demonstrated that the ring system was stable enough for isolation.

2. Structure of isoindole

Isoindole **1** is a bicyclic 10π electron array and complies with the Hückel ($4n + 2$) rule for aromatic stabilization⁴. There have been several calculations of the electronic structure of isoindoles^{5–8}. The distribution of charge density around the isoindole nucleus was calculated based

[†]The relevant literature on isoindolinones has been reviewed through December 2000.

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on the LACO-MO method or the 'frontier electron concept', and the relatively high electron density found at position-1. Therefore, the expectation is that electrophilic substitution on carbon will occur most readily at this position. The semiempirical calculations of Dewar, and Polansky and Derflinger estimate a substantial degree of resonance stabilization for isoindole with a value of about 56 kcal mol^{-1} which is significantly larger than the value of pyrrole and is close to that ascribed for indole. Isoindole **1** should be favored over its tautomer, isoindolenine **3** by about 8 kcal mol^{-1} according to a molecular orbital calculation of Veber and Lwowski⁹. Theoretical studies by Dewar *et al.*¹⁰ are consistent with structure **1**

3. Naturally occurring isoindole and isoindolinone (phthalimidine) derivatives

The first isoindolobenzazepine alkaloid (\pm)-chilenine **7** has been found in *Berberis empetrifolia* Lam. (Berberidaceae) by Fajardo *et al.*¹¹. Valencia *et al.*¹² isolated nuevamine **8**, the first known isoindoloisoquinoline alkaloid and lennoxamine **9**, an isoindolobenzazepine structurally related to (\pm)-chilenine from *Berberis darwinii* Hook (Berberidaceae).

Valencia *et al.*¹³ also isolated a series of novel isoindolobenzazepines including (\pm)-13-deoxychilenine **10**, pictonamine **11**, chileninone **12**, (\pm)-chilenamine **13**, and (\pm)-palmanine **14** from three Chilean *Berberis* species, namely, *B. actinacantha* Mart. ex Schult., *B. darwinii* Hook and *B. valdiviana* Phil. The isolation of the first known isoindolobenzazocine alkaloid magallanesine **15** from *Berberis darwinii* Hook was also achieved by Valencia *et al.*¹⁴.

Staurosporine **16** containing an isoindolinone moiety was isolated from *Saccharothrix* Sp. AM-2282¹⁵, and has very interesting biological activities, such as antimicrobial^{16a}, hypotensive^{16b}, cytotoxic^{16c} activities. It is also an inhibitor of protein kinase^{16c}, and platelet aggregation^{16d}.

The naturally occurring isoindole(2,5-dimethyl-6-methoxy-4,7-dihydroisoindole-4,7-dione) **17** was isolated from sponge *Reniera* Sp.¹⁷.

A series of cytostatically active metabolites have been isolated from microorganisms in which a highly substituted hydrogenated isoindolone unit is fused to an 11- to 14-mem-

bered macrocycle. The isolation of the first two substances (cytochalasin B **18** and cytochalasin D **19**) of the cytochalasin series was achieved by Rothweiler and Tamm¹⁸ and Aldridge *et al.*¹⁹. The cytochalasins are a group of about two dozen structurally related fungal metabolites having a wide range of biological activities^{20a,b}.

4. Biologically important isoindole and isoindolinone (phthalimidine) derivatives

Heterocyclic compounds containing phthalimidine(2,3-dihydroisoindol-1-one) skeleton have outstanding biological and physicochemical activities, few of these are being cited here. The 1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrazino[2,1-*a*]isoindol-

6-one **20** was found to lower blood pressure in spontaneously hypertensive rats²¹. A new nonsteroidal antiinflammatory agent indoprofen **21** was synthesized by Li *et al.*²².

A novel promising anxiolytic drug is DN-2327, a non-benzodiazepine isoindoline derivative **22**, which has shown in animals to have anxiolytic, taming, antiaggressive and anticonvulsive effects without relevant sedative properties, or signs of dependence²³. DN-2327 showed a higher affinity for the BZ1-GABA receptor in comparison to diazepam or flunitrazepam.

Belliotti *et al.*²⁴ discovered a series of isoindolinone derivatives **23** having affinity for the dopamine D₄ receptor. Compounds containing substituents in 3- and 4-positions of the phenyl ring have the highest D₄ receptor affinity.

The synthesis of a group of cyclic amide analogs, e.g. **24** and **25** of 4-(2'-methoxyphenyl)-1-[2'-[N-(2''-pyridyl)-p-iodobenzamido]ethyl]piperazine (*p*-MPPI **26**) as 5-HT_{1A} receptor ligands was achieved by Zhuang *et al.*²⁵. Some of these compounds displayed very high *in vitro* binding affinity for 5-HT_{1A} receptors, comparable to or exceeding that of the parent compound **26**.

Norman *et al.*²⁶ prepared a series of isoindolinone derivatives **27** bridged to 4-(1,2-benzisothiazol-3-yl)-1-piperazinyl moiety with a variety of different bridging units. The compounds were evaluated *in vitro* at dopamine D₂ and serotonin 5-HT_{1a} and 5-HT₂ receptors and *in vivo* for their ability to antagonize the apomorphine-induced climbing response in mice and found as potential antipsychotic agents. A four-carbon spacer provided optimal activity within the homologous series.

3-(4-Acetoxyphenyl)methylene-2-(2-diethylamino)ethyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-isoindol-1-one **28** was found to exhibit local anesthetic activity superior to that of procaine²⁷.

Achinami *et al.*²⁸ prepared alkylidene isoindolinone derivatives **29** as vasodilators which exhibited IC₅₀ of 5.6 μM in inhibition of 40 mM K⁺-induced coronary contraction *in vitro* and inhibitory effect to the thromboxan A₂ analog (U-46619)-induced vasoconstriction. The isoindolo[2,1-*a*]quinolines of type **30** showed protective effect against N₂ induced hypoxia²⁹. Lippmann³⁰ prepared 1,3-dihydro-3-(2-hydroxy-2-methylpropyl]-2*H*-isoindol-1-one **31** and found it to be useful in the treatment of ulcers.

The study of cytotoxic effects³¹ of isoindol-1-one derivatives **32** and **33** on leukemia P388 cells showed that nearly half of the compounds inhibited uridine incorporation, but only three compounds affected incorporation of thymidine and L-valine. The cytotoxic effects of the compounds could be related not only to the types and position of the substituents but to stereoisomerism as well.

Mappicine ketone (MPK) **34**, an analog of mappicine **35**, a naturally derived alkaloid isolated from *Mapia foetida* Miers. (Olacaceae)^{32a} has been identified as an antiviral lead compound with selective activity against herpes viruses HSV-1, HSV-2 and human cytomegalovirus (HCMV). MPK appears to be herpes virus selective in that it does not inhibit other DNA or RNA viruses^{32b}.

Dihydrothiazoloisoindolones **36** were found to be potent non-nucleosidic HIV reverse transcriptase inhibitors³³.

Taylor *et al.*³⁴ synthesized a conformationally constrained analog **37b** of 5,10-dideaza-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrofolic acid

(DDATHF) **37a**, in which the glutamate moiety is tied back to the benzoyl ring through an isoindolinone moiety. The preliminary biological evaluation of **37b** revealed that it to be an excellent inhibitor of human CCRF-CEM lymphoblastic leukemic cells and a non-competitive inhibitor of mammalian glycylamide ribonucleotide formyltransferase.

Hexahydroisoindole **38** was found to be a potent herbicidal³⁵. Kim and Ryu³⁶ developed a synthetic method for the herbicidal 2,3-dihydro-3-methylene-2-substituted-phenyl-1*H*-isoindol-1-one derivatives. Compound **39** showed good herbicidal activity against various weed species.

Other important derivatives of isoindole are the metal complexes **40** of phthalocyanines, used as dyes and pigments^{37a,b}.

5. Isoindolinone in the synthesis of drugs

Isoindolinones (phthalimidines) have been widely used as intermediates for the synthesis of various important drugs. Shihunine, a popular Chinese drug, sold in Hong Kong, was isolated about 30 years ago by Inubushi *et al.*³⁸ from *Dendrobium iohonense* as a phthalide pyrrolidine alkaloid which they named shihunine as it was a component of Shi-Hu. Breuer and Zbaida³⁹ synthesized shihunine **41** from the lactam, spiro[(1-methylpyrrolidine)-2,3'-(2'-methyl-1'-isoindolinone)] **42** (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

A synthesis of pyrazino[2,1-*a*]isoindole derivative **44** via isoindolinone **43** was developed by Ferland *et al.*²¹ (Scheme 2). The analog, e.g. 1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrazino[2,1-*a*]isoindol-6-one **20** was found to lower blood pressure

in spontaneously hypertensive rats.

Scheme 2. Reagents : (i) MeOH, 1 *N* HCl, H₂, Pd/C, (ii) THF, 1 *M* diborane in THF.

Abramovitch *et al.*⁴⁰ obtained the ring expanded 2-benzazepin-1-one **46** through the reaction of 3-substituted-(1*H*)-1-isoindolones **45** (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Recently, Pigeon and Decroix⁴¹ developed a new approach to isoindolo[2,1-*b*]benzodiazepines **48** through an intramolecular cyclization of a *N*-substituted-3-hydroxy-isoindolinone **47** (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

6. Isoindolinones in the synthesis of natural products

Vedejs *et al.*⁴² reported the synthesis of isoindolone **49** having part of the structure of cytochalasin D **19**.

Marsili *et al.*⁴³ synthesized isoindolobenzazepinone derivative **51** which are structurally related to the alkaloid pictonamine **11**, from isoindolinone **50** (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

From isoindolinone derivatives **52** Napolitano *et al.*⁴⁴ synthesized the isoindolobenzazepine alkaloids lennoxamine

9 and chilenamine 13 (Scheme 6).

Recently, Othman and Decroix⁴⁵ reported a synthesis of benzo[*a*]pyrrolo[2,3-*f*]indolizine 54, a new heterocyclic analog of chilenine alkaloid 7, from the isoindolinone derivative 53 (Scheme 7).

Scheme 6

Scheme 7

Othman *et al.*⁴⁶ also developed a synthesis of benzo[*a*]thieno[*g*]indolizinones 56, polycyclic compounds analogous to the alkaloid nuevamine 8, via an intramolecular α -amidoalkylation reaction of isoindolinone derivative 55 with thionyl chloride (Scheme 8a).

Scheme 8a

Recently, Heaney and Shuhaibar⁴⁷ reported a synthesis of the alkaloid nuevamine skeleton, e.g. isoindoloisoquinoline derivative 58 from an α -methoxyisoindolone derivative 57 (Scheme 8b).

Scheme 8b

7A. Classical methods

7A.1. Synthesis of isoindolinones (phthalimidines) through Gabriel's procedure

In 1885 Gabriel developed⁴⁸ a general method for the synthesis of ylidenephthalides by condensation of phthalic anhydride 59 with arylacetic acid in the presence of sodium or potassium acetate at 230–250° (a type of Perkin reaction). He also reported that benzylidene phthalide 60 on treatment with ammonia in alcohol at 100° for 8–10 h yielded benzylidene phthalimidine 61 (Scheme 9).

Scheme 9

Honzl⁴⁹ reported the synthesis of methylene isoindolinone 63 by heating aniline and phthalylidene acetic acid 62 in acetic acid (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10

Perjessy *et al.*⁵⁰ reported the synthesis of 3-arylmethylene phthalimidines 66 through a Gabriel modification of Perkin condensation where phthalimide 64 was reacted with the corresponding arylacetic acids 65 (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

Scartoni *et al.*⁵¹ reported the synthesis of 3-benzyl-3-hydroxyphthalimidin-2-ylacetic acid 67 which yielded 3-benzylidene phthalimidin-2-ylacetic acid 68. This was subsequently converted to isoindolobenzazepine 69 (Scheme 12).

Scheme 12

A series of benzylidenes phthalimidines **71** were prepared starting from phthalic anhydride²⁷ **59**. A typical example is given in Scheme 13.

Scheme 13

7A.2. Alkylidene isoindolinones through Grignard procedure

Alkylidene isoindolinones (alkylidenephthalimidines) were synthesized by the action of a Grignard reagent on a *N*-substituted-phthalimide and subsequent dehydration⁵². Ang and Halton⁵³ applied the Grignard procedure reported by Heidenbluth *et al.*⁵² to prepare 2-substituted 3-alkyl-3-hydroxyphthalimidines **73** through the reaction of alkyl magnesium halide in ether on phthalimide **72** in benzene at 55° for 3 h. Dehydration of the alcohols **73** in concentrated sulfuric acid afforded the alkylidenephthalimidines **74** in good yields (Scheme 14).

$R_1, (R_2, R_3) = H (CO_2Et \text{ or } H) \text{ or } CO_2Et; Me (CO_2Et \text{ or } H) \text{ or } CO_2Et; Ph (Me \text{ or } H) \text{ or } Me, Ph (Me) Me; Ph (H) H; Me (Me \text{ or } H) \text{ or } Me, Me (Me) Me; Me (H) H; H (Me \text{ or } H) \text{ or } Me.$

Scheme 14

Recently, Achinami *et al.*²⁸ reported the synthesis of a series of alkylideneisoindolinone derivatives **77** by following the above Grignard procedure (Scheme 15).

$R_1 = (\text{substituted})\text{alkyl}, Ph, PhSO_4; R_2 = H, \text{alkoxy}, OH, \text{halo}, (\text{substituted})\text{alkyl}, \text{acyl}; R_3, R_4 = H, \text{alkyl}, \text{aryl}, \text{alkoxy}, OH; n = 0, 1, 2.$

Scheme 15

7A.3. Synthesis of isoindolinones through lithiation procedures

Watanabe *et al.*⁵⁴ reported a synthesis of 3-substituted-phthalimidines **80** from benzanilide **78** through lithiation with *n*-butyllithium and subsequent reaction with benzonitrile (Scheme 16).

Scheme 16

Parham *et al.*⁵⁵ prepared *N*-phenylphthalimidine **83** by selective halogen-lithium exchange in bromophenylalkylhalides **81** with *n*-butyllithium followed by treatment with phenyl isocyanate (Scheme 17).

Scheme 17

Parham and Jones⁵⁶ also synthesized *N*-phenylphthalimidine derivative **86** from 2-bromobenzonitrile **84** and *n*-butyllithium at -78° followed by the reaction with phenyl isocyanate (Scheme 18).

Scheme 18

An effective reaction of Schiff bases with certain functionalized organolithium reagents was described by Bradsher and Hunt⁵⁷ for the synthesis of 1,2-diarylisoindolines **87** (Scheme 19).

87: a) $Ar = Ar_1 = Ph$; b) $Ar = 4-Brc_6H_4, Ar_1 = Ph$; c) $Ar = 2-Br-4-MeC_6H_3, Ar_1 = Ph$; d) $Ar = Ph, Ar_1 = 3,4-(OCH_3)_2C_6H_3$.

Scheme 19

Hendi *et al.*⁵⁸ reported a Parham-type cyclization⁵⁹ in which *N*-acyl-2-bromobenzamides **88** participated in metal-halogen exchange with *n*-BuLi to form *N*-acyl-2-lithiobenzamides **89**. The resulting *ortho*-lithio intermediates **89** then underwent cyclization to afford 3-alkylidenephthalimidines **90** (Scheme 20).

Scheme 20

Campbell *et al.*⁶⁰ developed a synthesis of isoindolinones **94** through a lithiation procedure (Scheme 21).

Scheme 21. Reagents and conditions : (i) BF₃·OEt₂, -78°; (ii) PhLi, -78°; (iii) H₂O, warm to 50°, overnight.

Recently, Jozwiak and Sadokierska⁶¹ reported the synthesis of hydroxyazaisoindolinones and their successful conversion to azaisoindoleacetic acids as effective precursors for the corresponding 4*b*-phenyldihydroazaisoindol[2,1-*a*]quinolinediones **98** (Scheme 22).

Scheme 22. Reagents and conditions : (i) 1. BuLi, THF, -78 to 0°; 2. methyl benzoate, in THF, -78° to RT; (ii) diethylmalonate, methanesulfonic acid, (AcO)₂O, 100°; (iii) 20% HCl solution, heated upto boiling; (iv) 1. oxalylchloride, C₂H₄Cl₂, reflux, 0.2 h; 2. AlCl₃, C₂H₄Cl₂, reflux, 2 h.

Couture *et al.*⁶² recently reported that 2-alkyl-2,3-dihydroisoindol-1-ones **99** are easily and regioselectively deprotonated at the 3-position of the heterocyclic nucleus with LDA, thus providing ready access to 3-substituted and/or functionalized isoindolinones **100** and consequently to the corresponding isoindolines **101** (Scheme 23).

Scheme 23

A series of 3-substituted-isoindolinones **23** having affinity for the dopamine D₄ receptor was prepared by Belliotti *et al.*²⁴ starting from isoindolinoneacetic acid **102** (Scheme 24).

Scheme 24. Reagents : (i) NaH, DMF; (ii) MeI; (iii) NaBH₄, MeOH; (iv) *p*-TsCl, TEA in CH₂Cl₂.

Couture *et al.*⁶³ developed the synthesis of a series of 3-(alkyl and aryl)methylene-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-isoindol-1-one derivatives. Treatment of phosphorylated amides **104** with KHMDS (2.2 equiv.) in THF at -78° followed by quenching with selected aromatic and aliphatic carboxaldehydes affords a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers of 2-alkyl-3-(aryl and alkyl)methylene-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-isoindol-1-ones **105** (Scheme 25).

Scheme 25. Reagents and conditions : (i) KHMDS (2.2 equiv.), THF, -78° to RT 2 h; (ii) R₃CHO, THF, -30°; (iii) -30° to RT 0.5 h; (iv) aqueous HCl.

7A.4. 3-Alkylidene isoindolinones through Wittig reaction

Flitsch and Peters⁶⁴ synthesized 3-ethoxycarbonylmethyleneisoindolin-1-ones (phthalimidines) **106** from the reaction of phthalimides **72** with Wittig reagents at 140° (Scheme 26).

Scheme 26

Mali and Yeola⁶⁵ described a novel synthesis of *N*-substituted-3-carbomethoxymethylphthalimidines **110** from secondary benzamides through a combination of lithiation and Wittig reaction (Scheme 27).

107-110 a-e) $R_1 = H$, f) $R_1 = OCH_3$; a) $R_2 = CH_3$, b) $R_2 = Ph$, c) $R_2 = C_6H_4OMe-o$, d) $R_2 = C_6H_4OMe-m$, e) $R_2 = C_6H_4OMe-p$, f) $R_2 = Ph$

Scheme 27

Epszajn *et al.*⁶⁶ described the synthesis of the 3-hydroxy-5-azaisoindolin-1-ones **112** and their conversion to 2-aryl-2,3-dihydro-3-oxo-1*H*-azaisoindole-1-acetic acids **113** and subsequent cyclization to the corresponding dihydroazaisoindolo[2,1-*a*]quinolinediones **114** (Scheme 28).

Scheme 28. Reagents and conditions : (a) i. BuLi, THF, -78 to 0°; ii. DMF, -78 to 0°; (b) Wittig reagent, 170°, 0.7 h; (c) i. oxalyl chloride, Cl₂C₂H₄; ii. AlCl₃, Cl₂C₂H₄.

7A.5. Synthesis of isoindolinones through Diels-Alder reaction

An efficient approach for the synthesis of hexahydroisoindolones **118** was reported by Gutierrez *et al.*⁶⁷ (Scheme 29).

Scheme 29

An isoindolinone ring was synthesised through a series of steps which started with a Diels-Alder reaction of the Danishefsky diene **119** with 4,4-diethoxybut-2-ynal **120** by Taylor *et al.*³⁴ (Scheme 30).

Scheme 30

7A.6. Synthesis of isoindolinones through reduction processes

Brewster *et al.*⁶⁸ reduced *N*-alkylphthalimides **72** to phthalimidines **125** under Clemmensen condition (Scheme 31).

Scheme 31

Ciganek⁶⁹ prepared a mixture of *N*-4-pentylisoindole **127**, isoindoline **128** and isoindolinone **129** by the reduction of *N*-4-pentylphthalimide **126** with sodium bis(2-methoxyethoxy)aluminium hydride; *N*-4-pentylisoindole **127** was the major product (Scheme 32).

Scheme 32

Milewska *et al.*⁷⁰ reported a synthesis of *N*-methylisoindolinones **131** by regioselective reduction of **72** using Lawesson's reagent (LR) to yield monothioimides **130** followed by desulfurisation of **130** with Raney nickel (Scheme 33).

Scheme 33

A series of isoindolinone derivatives²⁶ **27a-c** attached to the 4-(1,2-benzisothiazol-3-yl)-1-piperazinyl moiety were prepared by a variety of methods (Scheme 34).

A method for the reduction of phthalimide to the 3-

Scheme 34. Reagents : (i) Ethanolanine or 3-amino-1-propanol, 205–210°; (ii) *trans*-4-aminocyclohexanol hydrochloride, K_2CO_3 , toluene, H_2O , reflux; (iii) SOCl_2 , toluene, 60°; (iv) Et_3N , CH_2Cl_2 , MsCl , 0°; (v) 3-(1-piperazinyl)-1,2-benzisothiazole, Et_3N , CH_3CN , reflux.

hydroxyisoindolinone **136** and a coupled product **137** was performed⁷¹ by a low-valent-titanium reagent in an aromatic solvent or in the absence of solvent (Scheme 35).

Scheme 35

The coupled product **137** (23%) and phthalimidine **138** (44%) were obtained in the absence of solvent. In *p*-xylene, three monomolecular reductive products were produced (phthalimidine **138** 24%, 3-hydroxyisoindolinone **136** 19% and phthalide **132** 11%); no coupling product was isolated.

Luzzio and Zacherl⁷² described the synthesis of isoindolinone (Scheme 36).

Scheme 36

Zhuang *et al.*²⁵ developed the synthesis of a group of isoindol-1-ones **24**, cyclic amide analogs of *p*-MPP1 **26** as 5-HT_{1A} receptor ligands (Schemes 37 and 38).

Scheme 37

Scheme 38

7A.7. Synthesis of isoindolinones through condensation reactions using phthalaldehyde as starting material

Yamamoto showed⁷³ that an equimolar mixture of phenyl isocyanate and phthalaldehyde **151** on heating at 170° for 4 h afforded *N*-phenylphthalimidine **152** (Scheme 39).

Scheme 39

DoMinh *et al.*⁷⁴ described a reaction of phthalaldehyde **151** with ammonia and amines in Me_2SO_4 (Scheme 40). Major products were phthalimidines **153** and 3-(2-cyanophenyl)isoquinoline **154**.

Scheme 40

Grigg *et al.*⁷⁵ investigated the reaction of *o*-phthalaldehyde **151** with α -amino acids **155** in boiling acetic acid and observed that a rapid reaction (5–10 min) occurred to give the *N*-substituted-isoindolin-1-ones **157** (Scheme 41) in good yield.

Scheme 41

A new route to isoindolinone derivatives was developed by Nefkens and Zwanenburg⁷⁶ as outlined in Scheme 42.

Scheme 42

Simons, Stobaugh and Takahashi, reported the quantitative formation of 2*H*-isoindole derivatives **168-170** (Scheme 43)⁷⁷⁻⁸¹.

Scheme 43

Allin *et al.*⁸² subsequently discovered that the reaction of α -amino acids **171** and amino alcohol **172** with *o*-phthalaldehyde **151** produced the corresponding phthalimidines **173** and **174**, respectively, in good yields (Scheme 44).

171 : L-valine, L-alanine, L-phenylalanine, L-serine, DL-leucine, DL-isoleucine; **173** : R = CH(CH₃)₂, CH₃, CH₂Ph, CH₂OH, CH₂CH(CH₃)₂, CHCH₃CH₂CH₃ respectively; **172** : 2-amino-3-methylbutanol, 2-amino-1-butanol, 2-amino-1-phenylpropanol, 2-amino-1-propanol; **174** : R₁/R₂ = CH(CH₃)₂/H, CH₂CH₃/H, CH₃/Ph, CH₃/H respectively.

Scheme 44

Recently, Allin *et al.*⁸³ have studied the reaction of α -amino alcohols **176** with 2-formylbenzoic acid **175** as part of an on-going investigation into the preparation and reactivity of the isoindolinone ring system. They have reported the extremely high diastereoselectivity of the reaction to produce the tricyclic γ -lactam products **177** (Scheme 45) through condensation of α -amino alcohols **176** with 2-formylbenzoic acid **175**. This class of heterocycles can act as *N*-acyliminium ion precursors in the synthesis of substituted-isoindolinone derivatives **179** (Scheme 46). The treatment of the (+/-)-valinol derived tricyclic lactam **178** with titanium tetrachloride at room temperature in dichloromethane prior to addition of allyl trimethylsilane afforded the desired substituted-isoindolinone **179** in 96% isolated yield.

176: (+/-) valinol, (S) phenylglycinol, (R) phenylglycinol, (S) phenylalaninol, (R) phenylalaninol; **177a** : R = Ph, CH₂Ph; **177b** : R = Ph, CH₂Ph;

Scheme 45

Scheme 46

7A.8. Synthesis of isoindolinones through rearrangement reactions

A new route to phenylmethyleisoindolinones was reported by Guillaumel *et al.*⁸⁴. The alkaline hydrolysis of 2-(2-benzofuranyl)benzonitriles **180** led to *Z*-2,3-dihydro-3-(2-hydroxyphenylmethylene)-(1*H*)-isoindolin-1-ones **183** by rearrangement (Scheme 47). The formation of the amide **181** or the acid **182** depended on the solvent used.

Scheme 47. Reagents and conditions : (i) KOH (3.2 equiv.), ethanol, reflux; (ii) KOH (3.2 equiv.), ethyleneglycol or methoxyethanol, reflux.

Heaney and Shuhaibar⁴⁷ developed a route to 3-methoxy-2-phenylethylisoindolin-1-one **57** which functions as a precursor to synthetically useful acyliminium ions (Scheme 48).

Scheme 48

7A.9. Synthesis of isoindolinones through photochemical reaction

Freccero *et al.*⁸⁵ reported a synthesis of 3-hydroxy-isoindolinones **187** by photochemical reactions of phthalimides **72** (Scheme 49).

Scheme 49

Weidner-Wells *et al.*⁸⁶ showed that *N*-methylphthalimide (NMP) **72** undergoes a photolysis reaction with phenylcyclopropane in acetonitrile to give two isomeric spiro-tetrahydrofuran lactams (**188** and **189**). When the reaction was carried out in the nucleophilic solvent MeOH, hydroxylactam **190** and 1-methoxy-3-phenylpropane were obtained (Scheme 50).

Scheme 50

Griesbeck *et al.*⁸⁷ photochemically transformed *N*-phthaloylcysteine derivative **191** by elimination, decarboxylation and via electron transfer cyclization to isoindolone derivatives **192** (Scheme 51). The excited singlets were prone to elimination and γ -H abstractions to yield compound **193** whereas the triplets on cyclization afforded 1,3,4,10*b*-tetrahydro-10*b*-hydroxy-6*H*-[1,4]thiazino[3,4-*a*]isoindol-6-ones **192**.

Scheme 51

7A.10. Synthesis of isoindolinones through miscellaneous processes

Rowe *et al.*⁸⁸ reported that the treatment of benzo-2'-nitrophenylhydrazide-2- β -acrylic acid **194a** with boiling dilute Na₂CO₃ solution, H₂O or nitrobenzene afforded 2-(2'-nitrophenylamino)isoindolinone-3-acetic acid **195a**. When isoindolinone derivative **195a** was boiled with acetic anhydride with or without addition of pyridine or refluxed with toluene in the presence of phosphorus trichloride, 1 molecule of water was eliminated, yielding 2,5-diketo-3-(2'-nitrophenyl)isoindolinopyrazolidocoline **196a** which was readily hydrolyzed to **195a** preferably by acids (Scheme 52). Similarly, other compounds **195b-e** and **196b-e** were synthesized.

Pojer *et al.*⁸⁹ prepared methyleneisoindolinone **198** by refluxing acetylbenzoic acid or its methyl ester **197** with aniline (Scheme 53).

An interesting approach to isoindolinone **200** was pub-

Scheme 52

Scheme 53

lished by Whelton and Huitric⁹⁰ involving the reaction of the nitrolactone **199** with bases. The reaction of **199** with aniline led to the phthalimidine **200** (Scheme 54).

Scheme 54

Camilleri and Cassola⁹¹ reported a reaction in which the 2-(1-aminoethyl)benzoate anion cyclised to the lactam 3-methylisoindolinone **203** at high pH. 2-(1-Aminoethyl)benzoic acid **201** (prepared by catalytic hydrogenation of the oxime of 2-acetyl benzoic acid) was cyclised in presence of 0.1 M NaOH to yield lactam **203**. They proposed the mechanism shown in Scheme 55.

Scheme 55

Kimura *et al.*⁹² synthesized a new macrocyclic polyamine **207** containing a phthalimidine ring (Scheme 56).

A general procedure for 2,3-dihydro-3-methylene-2-substituted-1*H*-isoindol-1-ones (3-methylenephthalimidines) **208** was developed by Howe and Shelton⁹³ (Scheme 57).

An improved method for the synthesis of phthalimidine-

Scheme 56

Scheme 57

3-carboxylate was reported by Othman and Decroix⁴⁵ (Scheme 58).

Scheme 58

A facile synthetic method for the herbicidal 2,3-dihydro-3-methylene-2-aryl-1H-isoindol-1-one system **218a-c** was described by Kim and Ryu³⁶ (Scheme 59).

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
214, 216, 218 a	H	H	F
b	H	H	Cl
c	H	OCH ₃	H
d	H	CH ₃	CH ₃
e	Cl	H	Cl

217, R₄X: a) propargyl bromide, b) ethyl iodide, c) 2-chloropropanitrile

Scheme 59

7B. Synthesis of isoindolinones through metal mediated reactions

Several methods of synthesis of isoindolinones (phthalimidines) under metal catalysis were discussed by Wilkinson *et al.*⁹⁴ where various starting compounds including Schiff bases, aromatic nitriles, ketoximes, phenylhydrazones, semicarbazones and azines have been carbonylated. A series of isoindolinones **220** were produced by the carbonylation of Schiff bases **219** of aromatic and aliphatic amines^{95,96}. The reaction was catalyzed by metal carbonyls like pentacarbonyl iron and octacarbonyl dicobalt. The best results were obtained from cobalt-catalyzed carbonylation which was performed in the temperature range 200–230° under a CO pressure of 100–200 bar (Scheme 60). The reaction was also catalyzed by Pd^{II}-acetate under milder condition (Scheme 61). Polar solvents were found to inhibit the reaction.

Scheme 60

Scheme 61

Phthalimidine derivative **223** was synthesized from the carbonylation of aromatic nitrile **222** under a pressure of CO containing variable amounts of hydrogen in the presence of a cobalt catalyst; the best yields were observed when a small quantity of pyridine was added to the reaction⁹⁷ (Scheme 62).

Scheme 62

3-Substituted-phthalimidines **225** were prepared from the carbonylation of aromatic ketoximes **224** in the presence of hydrogen and the catalyst octacarbonyl dicobalt. The reaction was more selective with diaryl ketoximes than with arylalkyl ketoximes⁹⁷ (Scheme 63).

Scheme 63

The same reaction applied to the *o*-methyl ether of benzophenone oxime resulted in 3-phenylphthalimidines.

It was reported that benzophenone phenyl hydrazones **226** gave rise to 3-phenylphthalimidine **227** in the presence of octacarbonyl di-cobalt without hydrogen gas at 190–200°, but at higher temperature (230–240°), 3-phenyl-*N*-(*N*-phenylcarbamoyl)phthalimidine **228** was obtained via insertion of CO into the nitrogen-nitrogen bond^{96,98} (Scheme 64).

Scheme 64

In the case of unsymmetrically substituted diaryl ketone phenyl hydrazones, e.g. **229**, a mixture of isomeric phthalimidines **230** and **231** were obtained (Scheme 65).

Scheme 65

Phthalimidine **233** was also prepared from acetophenone-1,1-dimethylhydrazone **232** through carbonylation reaction mediated by Pd^{II}-acetate under much milder conditions⁹⁸ (Scheme 66).

Scheme 66

3-Phenylphthalimidines **227** and **235** were obtained when benzophenone semicarbazone **234** reacted with CO in the presence of cobalt catalyst at higher temperature (245°)^{97,98} (Scheme 67).

Scheme 67

Benzaldehyde azine **236** also gave different *N*-substituted-phthalimidines **138** and **223** under the reaction with CO in the presence of cobalt catalyst (Scheme 68).

Scheme 68

Thompson and Heck⁹⁹ described the carbonylation of the palladium acetate complex **237** to yield 3-acetoxy-2-phenylphthalimidine **240**. The carbonylation of **237** in presence of a nucleophile, e.g. aniline, led to 3-anilino-2-phenylphthalimidines **241** rather than the acetate (Scheme 69).

Scheme 69

Mori *et al.*¹⁰⁰ developed a synthesis of benzolactams, i.e. isoindolinone, isoquinoline and benzazepinone derivatives by palladium catalyzed amidation. In a typical example, *N*-benzyl-*o*-bromobenzylamine **242** was treated with *n*-Bu₃N, PPh₃ and a catalytic amount of Pd(OAc)₂ in presence of CO at 100° for 26 h to afford *N*-benzylisoindolin-1-one **243** (Scheme 70).

Scheme 70

However, *o*-bromo-*N*-(*o*'-bromobenzyl)phenylethylamine **244**, was cyclized to yield isoindolinone **245** and isoquinolinone **246** in a 2.6 : 1 ratio under the same conditions (Scheme 71).

Scheme 71

Brunet *et al.*¹⁰¹ developed cobalt carbonyl catalyzed carbonylation of arylhalides **247** under phase-transfer-catalysis conditions for the synthesis of benzolactam **249** (Scheme 72).

Scheme 72

Dikshit¹⁰² reported a novel reaction of 3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-3,4-dihydro-1-oxo-1*H*-2-benzopyran-4-carboxylic acid **250a** and 3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-1-oxo-1*H*-2-benzopyran-4-carboxylic acid **250b** to yield 2,3-dihydro-3-arylmethylene-1*H*-isoindol-1-ones **253a,b** (Scheme 73).

Scheme 73

Larock *et al.*¹⁰³ carried palladium-promoted olefination reaction of thallated *N*-methylbenzamide **254** with methyl acrylate to yield an isoindolinone **255** (Scheme 74).

Scheme 74

Grigg *et al.*¹⁰⁴ reported intramolecular Heck reactions for the preparation of isoindolinone derivatives **257**, **258**, **260–262** (Scheme 75).

Scheme 75

Burns *et al.*¹⁰⁵ developed a palladium-catalyzed tandem cyclization-anion capture process. They reported that enamide **263** undergoes regioselective 5-exo trig-biscyclization (DMF, 80°) followed by hydride capture to afford the tricyclic products **264** (Scheme 76).

Scheme 76. Reagents and conditions : (i) Pd(OAc)₂, PPh₃, Bu₄NCl, sodium formate, DMF or CH₃CN, 80°/100°, 6/16 h.

Cho *et al.*¹⁰⁶ synthesised isoindolinones **266** via carbonylative cyclization of 2-(2-bromophenyl)-2-oxazolines **265** by a bimetallic palladium nickel catalyst system with carbon monoxide (3 atm) in alcohol as shown in Scheme 77.

Scheme 77. Reagents and conditions : PdCl₂(PPh₃)₂, NiCl₂, 6H₂O, PPh₃, Et₃N, 3 atm, 100°.

A synthesis of tricyclic isoindolinone **269** by the palladium-catalyzed carbonylative cyclization of 2-bromobenzaldehyde **267** with diamines **268** was carried out by Cho *et al.*¹⁰⁷ (Scheme 78).

Scheme 78. Reagents and conditions : (i) 2-Bromobenzaldehyde (2 mmol), ethylenediamine (3 mmol), (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂ (0.03 mmol), PPh₃ (0.08 mmol), Et₃N (5 mmol), CH₃CN (10 ml), CO (13 atm), 100°, 20 h.

8. Synthesis of isoindolinones through palladium-copper catalyzed reactions

Recently, Kundu and Khan¹⁰⁸ have reported a new strategy for the regio- and stereoselective synthesis of isoindolin-1-ones **273**, **274** through the palladium-catalyzed condensation of *o*-iodobenzamides **270** with terminal alkynes **271** and subsequent cyclization (Scheme 79). In most of the cases a number of (*Z*)-3-alkyl(aryl)ideneisoindolin-1-ones **274** were formed without any formation of the corresponding isoquinolinones. Only in a few cases, a mixture of isoindolinones **274** and isoquinolinones **275** were obtained. The configuration of 3-alkyl(aryl)ideneisoindolinones as *Z* was established by NMR studies and confirmed by X-ray diffraction studies¹⁰⁹.

Hydrogenation of 3-methyleneisoindolinones **273** afforded 3-methylisoindolinones **276** (Scheme 80). Hydrogenation of 3-arylideneisoindolinones **274** gave 3-benzylisoindolinones **277**.

Scheme 79

Scheme 80

Kundu *et al.*¹¹⁰ have also described another novel and facile procedure to 3-alkylideneisoindolinones under mild conditions. In this case, a palladium-catalyzed reaction was followed by Friedel-Crafts acylation and simultaneous cyclization to yield 3-alkylideneisoindolinones in good to excellent yields. *N*-Alkyl- or *N*-aryl-2-iodobenzamides **270** underwent facile reaction with trimethyl silyl acetylene, in the presence of $(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{PdCl}_2$ and CuI at room temperature to yield 2-(trimethylsilyl)ethynylbenzamides **278** in excellent yields (76–89%). 2-Trimethylsilyl ethynylbenzamides were then subjected to Friedel-Crafts reaction with acid chlorides or acetic anhydride to afford the 3-acylmethylideneisoindolinones **279** in good yields (Scheme 81).

Scheme 81

We have found that some of the isoindolinones **279** were in (*E*)-configuration while the rest were in the (*Z*)-configuration. The configuration of the 3-acylmethylideneisoindolinones was confirmed by X-ray crystallography¹¹¹.

Kundu *et al.*¹¹² have also reported the palladium-cata-

lyzed heteroannulation reaction of 2-iodobenzamides **270** with acetylenic carbinols **280** containing a terminal acetylenic group with a carbinol group next to it to afford 3-acylmethyl-isoindolinones **282** instead of the expected 3-alkylidene-isoindolinone **281** (Scheme 82).

Scheme 82

Conclusion

Isoindolinones are an important group of heterocyclic compounds which occur naturally and are also of biological importance. There have been many procedures available for the synthesis of this group of compounds. However, no recent review of this field is available in literature¹. In this report we have attempted to bring together the information available on the natural occurrence, biological importance and synthetic methodologies available for this group of compounds. We hope this will be of interest to many organic and medicinal chemists active in this area and stimulate more activities in this promising area.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. John Boulton of the University of East Anglia for reading the manuscript and helpful suggestions. One of the authors (R.M.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a Fellowship.

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